

HIGH-CONCENTRATION 35 KDA HYALURONIC ACID FRAGMENT GEL NIGHTTIME OCCLUSIVE APPLICATION FOR RAPID RELIEF OF TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINT PAIN AND ASSOCIATED MUSCLE OVER-TENSION: A CASE SERIES STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Temporomandibular joint disorder (TMD) is characterized by jaw joint pain and muscle over-tension, often accompanied by bruxism or jaw clenching, severely impacting quality of life. This exploratory case series evaluated the efficacy of 10% high-concentration 35 kDa hyaluronic acid fragment gel (HA35 Gel) as a nighttime occlusive treatment for TMD-related symptoms. Seven adult participants with TMD (6 males, 1 female; mean age 36.4 ± 2.8 years) applied ≥ 6.5 mL HA35 Gel to the TMJ area nightly, occluded with plastic wrap/skin protection film for 8-12 hours. Pain and muscle tension were assessed via a 0-10 numerical rating scale (NRS) at baseline, 60 seconds post-treatment, and 12 hours post-treatment. Results showed rapid, significant improvements: pain scores decreased from 4.0 ± 0.8 (baseline) to 0.1 ± 0.3 at 60 seconds and 0.0 ± 0.0 at 12 hours; muscle tension scores declined from 3.0 ± 0.8 to 0.4 ± 0.7 and 0.0 ± 0.0 , respectively. No adverse reactions were reported, indicating good tolerance. This non-invasive method

provides rapid (within 60 seconds) and sustained (≥ 12 hours) relief, offering a novel clinical option for TMD. Further validation in large-scale controlled studies is warranted.

KEYWORDS: Hyaluronic acid fragment; Temporomandibular joint disorder; TMD; Occlusive application; Pain relief; Muscle tension.

INTRODUCTION

TMD is a common jaw and facial disease in adults, with the peak incidence between ages 20 and 40. In the United States alone, approximately 10 million people are affected by TMD.^[1] The core pathological manifestations include pain and muscle over-tension in the jaw joint and the muscles that control jaw movement, often accompanied by headaches, restricted chewing function, and, if untreated, chronic pain and complications like tooth wear.^[2,3] The causes of TMD are complex, including jaw injury, bruxism, arthritis, and malocclusion.^[4] Currently, clinical treatment mainly consists of heat/cold compresses and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, but these therapies are often slow-acting and present safety concerns with long-term use.^[5]

In recent years, the biological activity of hyaluronic acid fragments with specific molecular weights has gained attention. Compared to high-molecular-weight hyaluronic acid, low-molecular-weight hyaluronic acid fragments can modulate sensory nerve signaling pathways and inflammation, exerting rapid analgesic effects.^[8,9] Our team's recent research confirmed that 10% high-concentration 35 kDa hyaluronic acid fragment gel (HA35 Gel) applied topically can relieve skin itching and superficial pain in a very short time. Pharmacokinetic studies have shown that the molecule does not penetrate deeply into tissues within 60 seconds, suggesting that its biological effect may rely on a non-traditional transdermal absorption mechanism.^[1,10] Building on these findings, this study further investigates the effect of HA35 Gel applied with a nighttime occlusive dressing to the temporomandibular joint area on pain and muscle over-tension, offering a new approach for clinical treatment.

CASES AND METHODS

Participant Information

This case series involved seven adult participants who met the diagnostic criteria for TMD. Among them, six were male, and one was female, aged between 32 and 40 years, with an average age of 36.4 ± 2.8 years. All participants signed an informed consent form and voluntarily participated in the study, completing the entire intervention and assessment without any dropouts.

Clinically, all participants had clear histories of TMJ pain and associated muscle over-tension for 1-6 months, with an average duration of 3.2 ± 1.5 months. Four participants reported intermittent pain and muscle tightness, which worsened after fatigue, staying up late, or stress. Three participants had persistent symptoms affecting daily chewing, speaking, and sleep. All participants exhibited bruxism or jaw clenching during sleep, with five participants describing significant bruxism symptoms, experiencing jaw stiffness and soreness upon waking. Two participants had unconscious jaw clenching during the day, with long-term muscle soreness. Additionally, two participants had mild tension-type headaches (related to excessive jaw muscle tension), with no other related jaw or facial diseases. None of the participants had received any TMD-specific treatments (including oral medications, physical therapy, or blocking treatments) within the previous two weeks and had not used any topical pain-relieving or anti-inflammatory agents.

Regarding their overall health, all participants were healthy adults with no severe systemic diseases (e.g., cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, autoimmune diseases, liver/kidney dysfunction, etc.), no history of skin allergies, local skin damage (e.g., TMJ area ulcers, eczema, dermatitis, etc.), or keloid formation. Physical exams showed no redness, swelling, or deformities in the TMJ area, but tenderness was present on palpation of the jaw joint, masseter muscle, and temporal muscle. Mouth opening was within the normal range (3.0-3.5 cm), with no limitations or deviation on opening. Neurological exams showed no abnormalities, and there were no other symptoms of pain or muscle tension elsewhere. Laboratory tests (blood routine, liver/kidney function) were all within normal ranges, with no significant abnormalities, excluding potential diseases that might affect the study's results. All participants were fully capable of independent judgment, proficient in using a standardized 0-10 NRS, and were able to self-assess and report pain and muscle over-tension at different time points.

Intervention

All participants followed the same intervention protocol: each evening, before sleep, after cleaning the skin, 10% HA35 Gel (Product No. Q/0285HND045) was evenly applied to the TMJ area, ensuring the gel fully covered the target area with a minimum amount of 6.5 mL. Immediately after application, the area was covered with plastic wrap or a skin protection film to prevent the gel from drying too early. The occlusion was maintained for 8-12 hours

overnight, and participants cleaned the treated area the following morning. This study was a single-intervention observation, with a focus on recording the effects at different time points.

Evaluation Methods

Pain and muscle tension were quantitatively assessed using a standardized 0-10 numerical rating scale.^[2,4] The specific scoring criteria were as follows: TMJ Pain Score: 0 represents "no pain," and 10 represents "theoretically the worst possible pain." Muscle Over-Tension Score: 0 represents "no muscle over-tension," and 10 represents "theoretically the worst possible muscle over-tension."

Evaluations were performed at baseline (pre-treatment), 60 seconds after treatment, and 12 hours after treatment.

RESULTS

All seven participants completed the full intervention and assessment, with no dropouts, and reported no local irritation, burning, allergies, or systemic side effects, indicating good safety and tolerance for this occlusive dressing protocol.

Regarding TMJ pain improvement (Table 1): The baseline score was 4.0 ± 0.8 , which rapidly decreased to 0.1 ± 0.3 after 60 seconds. Five participants reported a pain score of zero. After 12 hours, all participants had a pain score of zero, achieving complete relief.

Table 1: TMJ Pain Scores Before and After Treatment (0-10 Scale).

Participant Information	Pre-Treatment	60 Seconds After Treatment	12 Hours After Treatment
Male, 36 years old	3	0	0
Male, 32 years old	3	0	0
Female, 37 years old	4	0	0
Male, 39 years old	4	0	0
Male, 40 years old	4	0	0
Male, 32 years old	5	0	0
Male, 39 years old	5	1	0
Mean \pm SD	4.0 ± 0.8	$0.1 \pm 0.3^*$	$0.0 \pm 0.0^{**}$

Note: Statistical significance based on comparison with pre-treatment scores: * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$

Regarding muscle over-tension improvement (Table 2): The baseline score was 3.0 ± 0.8 , which decreased to 0.4 ± 0.7 after 60 seconds. Most participants experienced significant

symptom reduction. After 12 hours, all participants had a muscle over-tension score of zero, with stable effects.

Table 2: Muscle Over-Tension Scores Before and After Treatment (0-10 Scale).

Participant Information	Pre-Treatment	60 Seconds After Treatment	12 Hours After Treatment
Male, 36 years old	2	0	0
Male, 32 years old	2	0	0
Female, 37 years old	3	0	0
Male, 39 years old	3	0	0
Male, 40 years old	3	0	0
Male, 32 years old	4	1	0
Male, 39 years old	4	2	0
Mean \pm SD	3.0 \pm 0.8	0.4 \pm 0.7*	0.0 \pm 0.0**

Note: Statistical significance based on comparison with pre-treatment scores: *P<0.05, **P<0.01.

DISCUSSION

This case series is the first to confirm that the 10% HA35 Gel, when applied to the TMJ area with a nighttime occlusive dressing, can rapidly and effectively relieve related pain and muscle over-tension, with sustained effects. Improvement was seen 60 seconds after treatment, reaching complete relief within 12 hours. This rapid onset of action significantly outperforms traditional heat compresses and oral medications [5], and no adverse effects were observed, showing a clear safety advantage. The use of a 0-10 numerical rating scale to assess pain and muscle tension ensures the scientific reliability of the results.

Pharmacokinetic studies indicate that HA35 Gel does not penetrate deeply into the TMJ and deep muscle tissues within 60 seconds,^[10] suggesting that its analgesic and muscle-relieving effects may not rely on traditional transdermal absorption mechanisms. Based on previous research from our team,^[1,9] it is hypothesized that the mechanism involves the 35 kDa hyaluronic acid fragments modulating TRP ion channels in sensory nerve endings at the skin or mucosal surface and local inflammation pathways, rapidly lowering the pain threshold, thus achieving quick relief.^[8] This mechanism is similar to the anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties of hyaluronic acid in naked mole-rat tissues,^[6] further supporting the potential role of hyaluronic acid fragments as neuro-modulatory molecules.

Furthermore, the nighttime occlusion method effectively prevents the gel from drying out too early, ensuring a higher local concentration and adequate retention time of the drug, which

may be one of the key factors in its superior effectiveness compared to simple open application. In clinical practice, treatments for temporomandibular joint disorders still have limitations. Oral NSAIDs may cause gastrointestinal discomfort and other systemic side effects, while physical therapy is slow to act and requires professional guidance.^[5] In contrast, the HA35 Gel occlusive dressing protocol used in this study is simple, non-invasive, safe, and rapid-acting, providing a new non-invasive option for treating TMD, filling a gap left by traditional therapies.^[1,5]

While this study is innovative, it does have some limitations. The sample size was small, and the evaluation method mainly relied on subjective ratings (using the NPRS), lacking objective indicators like imaging or electrophysiology. Additionally, this study did not have a control group, nor did it assess long-term effects or repeated use. Future studies could expand the sample size, design randomized controlled trials, and incorporate objective evaluation methods^[1,5] to further clarify the mechanism, long-term effects, and suitable patient population for this hyaluronic acid fragment.

CONCLUSION

The 10% HA35 Gel applied to the TMJ area with a nighttime occlusive dressing provides rapid pain and muscle tension relief within 60 seconds, with stable effects lasting over 12 hours. It is safe, simple to use, and highly effective. This study suggests that HA35 Gel could become a novel, non-invasive treatment for TMD-related symptoms, offering a more efficient and safer clinical option and warranting further investigation.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

CONSENT AND ETHICS STATEMENT

Written informed consent was obtained from the patients for the publication of any potentially identifiable images or data included in this article.

REFERENCES

1. Xu F, Jia X, Hui J, Gorbunova V, Hui M. Analgesic effect of high-concentration 35 kDa hyaluronic acid fragment gel in herpes zoster-related pain: a case series. *Journal of Biosciences and Medicine*. In press.

2. Cleland JA, Childs JD, Whitman JM. Psychometric properties of the Neck Disability Index and Numeric Pain Rating Scale in patients with mechanical neck pain. *Arch., Phys., Med., Rehabil.* 2008; 89(1): 69–74.
3. Vernon H, Mior S. The Neck Disability Index: a study of reliability and validity. *J Manipulative Physiol., Ther.*, 1991; 14(7): 409–415.
4. Euasobhon P, Atisook R, Bumrunghatudom K, Zinboonyahgoon N, Saisavoey N, Jensen MP. Reliability and responsiveness of pain intensity scales in individuals with chronic pain. *Pain.* 2022; 163: e1184–e1191.
5. Dutheil F, Palgen C, Brousse G, Coste A, Saurin J, Lambert C, Pélissier C. Validation of visual analog scales of mood and anxiety at the workplace. *PLoS One.* 2024; 19: e0316159.
6. Zhang Z, Tian X, Lu JY, Boit K, Ablaeva J, Tolibzoda Zakusilo F, Emmrich S, Firsanov D, Rydkina E, Biashad SA, Lu Q, Tyshkovskiy A, Gladyshev VN, Horvath S, Seluanov A, Gorbunova V. Increased hyaluronan by naked mole-rat Has2 improves healthspan in mice. *Nature.* 2023; 621: 196–205.
7. Takasugi M, Firsanov D, Tomblin G, Ning H, Ablaeva J, Seluanov A, Gorbunova V. Naked mole-rat very-high-molecular-mass hyaluronan exhibits superior cytoprotective properties. *Nat., Commun.*, 2020; 11: 2376.
8. Ma X, Shofaro J, Jia X, Ma Z, Hui M. The low molecular weight hyaluronan fragment HA35 serves as a dual antagonist of pain-related calcium channels TRPV1 and TRPA1. *J Pharm., Res., Int.*, 2025; 37(6): 38–51.
9. Jia X, Shi M, Wang Q, Hui J, Shofaro JH, Erkhembayar R, Hui M, Gao C, Gantumur MA. Anti-inflammatory effects of the 35 kDa hyaluronic acid fragment (B-HA/HA35). *J Inflamm., Res.*, 2023; 16: 209–224.
10. Gantumur MA, Jia X, Hui JH, Barber C, Wan L, Furenlid LR, Martin DR, Hui M, Liu Z. Characterization, bioactivity, and biodistribution of 35 kDa hyaluronan fragment. *Life (Basel).* 2024; 14(1): 97.